

The First Record of the Genus *Xanthoectroma* Mercet (Chalcidoidea: Encyrtidae) in Ukraine

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The genus *Xanthoectroma* Mercet, 1925 includes single species, *X. aquilinum* Mercet, 1925, known as the parasitoid of mealybugs (Pseudococcidae) on cereals (Trjapitzin, 1989). I appreciate the kindness of Galina Stetsun, who collected the one female of *X. aquilinum* on

the island of Dzharylgach to the Moericke trap.

The material is deposited in I. I. Schmalhausen Institute of Zoology, National Academy of Sciences of Ukraine (Kyiv). Specimen was identified using the keys of V.A. Trjapitzin (1989).

Xanthoectroma aquilinum Mercet, 1925 (Fig. 1)

Material. Ukraine: Kherson Region, Skadovsk, Dzharylgach Island, 46.02N, 32.90E, 19.06.2019, 1 ♀ (G. Stetsun) (SIZK).

Distribution. Armenia, Czech Republic, Hungary, Kazakhstan (Dzhambul Region), Mongolia, Slovakia, Spanish mainland; East Palaearctic (Trjapitzin, 1989; Fauna Europea, 2019); Ukraine (**first record**).

Fig. 1. *Xanthoectroma aquilinum*, female, in alcohol, lateral view.

References

- Trjapitzin, V.A. 1989. *Parasitic Hymenoptera of the Fam. Encyrtidae of Palaearctics*. Nauka, Leningrad: 1–488 (Opredeliteli po faune SSSR izdavavaemiye Zoologicheskim Institutom AN SSSR, 158). [in Russian].
Fauna Europea. 2019. Available from: https://fauna-eu.org/cdm_dataportal/taxon/90cf28d2-cb39-49dc-9872-60900fc78b54. Accessed 12.09.2019.